

INTEGER

INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION
ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS

TERMS OF REFERENCE

EU-INTEGER Co-laboratory

on Health and Wellbeing

v.2, July 2024

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Background and introduction - The INTEGER project

INTEGER 4H- INTERCONNECTING 4 HELIX INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS IN EUROPEAN REGIONS is a Horizon Europe project funded by the European Innovation Council¹. It focuses on the generation of a meta-network or network of networks of actors who are addressing the challenges of Healthy Living and Well-being from different fields and approaches. INTEGER aims to deliver three essential innovations for the development of more robust, sustainable, inclusive and integrative European innovation ecosystems:

1. The development of a Col-laboratory model (INTEGER 4Helix) to promote the next generation of laboratories, the "Living Labs", which in Catalonia will be based on the Col-laboratori Catalunya initiative

2. The design of a Col-laboratory for Healthy Living and Well-being at the European level, as a community of networks with the capacity to work on real social, technological and business projects to promote more integrated and interconnected innovations; and
3. The creation of a new professional profile, the "col-laber" or "col-laboratory manager" as a multiplier agent of change in these integrated innovation ecosystems.

Finally, the project seeks to identify minimally viable products and services in the field of health and wellbeing through win-win collaborative dynamics where different actors can benefit.

More info: - Website <https://integercollab.eu>
 - Digital Platform <https://integer4h.theglobal.network>

¹ This is a project of the Horizon Europe framework programme, under the topic: '[HORIZON-EIE-2022-CONNECT-01-02: Integration of social innovation actor in innovation ecosystems](#)', which was submitted on 26 April 2022, was approved in July and will be launched on 1 February 2023 for 2 years, ending on 31 January 2025. INTEGER members will be appointed for the entire duration of the project.

Purpose - Why is an EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being necessary?

The importance of this initiative lies in its aim to provide a methodology and a pioneering platform to strengthen collaboration between actors, initiatives and projects in the field of health and well-being, starting with three European regions (Catalonia, Hamburg and Krakow). The ultimate goal is to extend to other European regions and international environments and to establish the INTEGER model as a basis for challenge-driven thematic partnerships. INTEGER is committed to co-creation dynamics and Quadruple Helix knowledge flows (academia, business sector, public bodies and social entities and citizens) that can lead to more robust and connected **innovation ecosystems, where social, business and technological innovation build bridges to generate positive impacts aligned with the approaches of the Triple Transition: Social, Ecological and Digital.**

In addition, the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory has **five capacity-multiplying breakthrough** innovations for the integration of social innovation into European innovation ecosystems:

- 1) Promote win-win dynamics in which all the agents involved are winners, accentuating the connection between business and social innovations that address common challenges;
- 2) Translating co-creation dynamics into new disruptive and tangible products, services or competences.
- 3) Co-design public innovation policies.
- 4) Develop training for the new generation of socio-digital entrepreneurs and facilitators of innovation ecosystems, the 'col-labers'; and
- 5) Devise funding and investment mechanisms for social innovation start-ups and SMEs to develop and expand their innovative capabilities.

What is the EU Integer Col-laboratory of Health and Well-being?

This is a non-formal agile structure to facilitate collaboration and to boost innovation (**social business and technology driven**) among partners from the quadruple helix.

The EU INTEGER Col-laboratory is a neologism to express the next generation of quadruple or n-helix living labs. They are cooperative instruments based on a peer-to-peer approach between business/social/technology-driven innovations. The INTEGER project has as a main aim to generate the 4H INTEGER Col-laboratory comprehensive model. It is a model that, although based on the regional triple helix dynamics, goes beyond it to include the quadruple helix (citizens and social entities and actors) in the innovation processes.

Target stakeholders

The INTEGER EU Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being will continuously incorporate interested agents:

- representing the quadruple helix.
- working on healthy living and well-being related issues.
- coming from social, business and/or technology-driven innovations.

- expressing their interest in aligning experiences and networking and collaboration efforts in the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being.

The following categories of actors and collaborating entities are applicable: academia, research organisations, industry, private companies, public institutions, users, workforce, non-governmental organisations, clusters, associations, investors, philanthropists, among others.

Why do we need you?

Based on its philosophy, the INTEGER project is committed to co-creation and expanding knowledge frontiers from an **interdisciplinary, intersectoral and international perspective**. It opens its doors to any actor interested in collaborating and contributing to the project.

The involvement of stakeholders is a win-win situation for both the project and for each actor or initiative involved:

- **Exchange** experiences and gather knowledge on the expected impact on health and well-being actions.
- **Identify** gaps from all possible perspectives to address society's needs in the health and well-being field.
- **Address** the benefits and future challenges in the different areas related to health and well-being in different dimensions and settings (technological, economic, environmental, political, social and ethical).
- **Identify** barriers and risks to collaboration that need to be addressed jointly to multiply the positive impact of actions taken by different actors and initiatives.
- **Anticipate** the changes needed at various scales to foster good practices regarding skills and competencies, boosting innovation ecosystems and more coordinated and systemic policies (health, innovation, education, employment, industry).

- **Identify** social, societal and environmental values to be preserved in the innovation process, e.g. social and territorial inclusiveness, reduction of environmental impact, and ecological sustainability.
- **Generate** synergies and build on good practices and positive results of past and ongoing initiatives.
- **Contribute** to gradually building a dynamic and sustainable community, ensuring an ongoing dialogue and connection between stakeholders.

Benefits of participating in the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being

- **Exchange** experiences and knowledge with the rest of the actors involved.
- **Opportunity** to learn from transformations and advances in other sectors.
- **Co-design** and prioritise future facilitating actions.
- **Opportunity** to be part of a pioneering platform in the European health field.
- **To develop and strengthen** beneficial collaborations in the medium-long term.

Roles, responsibilities and commitments

The participation in the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory for Health and Well-being does not imply any formal contractual commitment, as it means that you or your Organisation would like to take part and collaborate in the initiatives promoted by the members of this vibrant and growing quadruple helix community.

Members of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being are invited to contribute voluntarily during:

- Plenary meetings, webinars, workshops and focus group discussions (2-3 per year),
- Col-laborathons (Hackathons organised under the framework and principles of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory).
- Other initiatives that may arise from the quadruple helix collaborative dynamics of the platform (proposals, projects, etc.)

These initiatives will allow generating a dynamic community throughout the project and beyond.

The EU INTEGER Col-laboratory will work as a bidirectional channel, i.e. its members can contact INTEGER to communicate their needs and requests for support. In addition, project members are invited to help publicise the project by sharing their news and advances, fostering the assimilation of the project results and facilitating their assimilation in their organisations and administrations.

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List of actions arising from the Community

The following is just an overview of the type of activities that might arise from the quadruple helix dynamics facilitated in the Col-laboratory:

- **Exchange and integration** of good practices
- Generation of **project ideas**
- Preparation of **proposals for open calls**
- **Scaling** of Minimum Viable Products or Services
- **Invitation to new entities** to become part of the community, so that it can grow and become more robust. This shows the openness to 4H entities that are working in health and well-being with an interest in generating multi level dynamics
- **Exchange** of news
- **Training** and capacity building
- Access to the **quadruple helix** model
- Work on the basis of **collective intelligence**
- **Share and acquire** know-how

How to join EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being? - Participate and join in

To join the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory on Health and Well-being, please, fill out and sign **this [membership form](#)** to join the community.

The active participation of quadruple helix actors is channelled through [Theglocal.network](https://integer4h.theglocal.network), <https://integer4h.theglocal.network>, the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory co-creation digital space. There, actors generate content (events, posts, etc.), initiatives and projects at local, regional, inter-regional, European and international levels in a flexible and adaptable manner with the support of the Col-labers (the Col-laboratory facilitators) to ease that people connect and start co-creating.

You can also follow the INTEGER project activities through the [INTEGER website](https://integercollab.eu) <https://integercollab.eu>, where you can access all the content of the project, as well as the latest updates, news and other resources.

Fees and expenses

The EU INTEGER Col-laboratory stakeholder members will not receive project fees or fundings from the INTEGER project and or community.

Conflict of interests and confidentiality

As a member of the EU INTEGER Col-laboratory, the signatory party will not participate in any discussion in which a personal or professional situation or circumstance may compromise his or her ability to provide advice and recommendations in order to best fulfil their objectives and tasks.

INTEGER members shall respect the confidentiality of the proceedings and protect any information whose disclosure could harm the interests of the project.

Barcelona, July 20th 2024

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Hand signatories during the OLLD in September 2023

Name	Position	Signature
Manel Balcells	Catalan Ministry of Health, Government of Catalonia, Minister for Health	
Sergi Marcen	Secretary of Telecommunications and Digital Transformation, Government of Catalonia	
Kai Schnackenber	Free and Hanseatic City of Hamburg; Ministry of Labour, Health, Social, Family Affairs and Integration. Deputy head of division for international affairs and innovation	
Ramon Maspons	Catalan Ministry of Health, Government of Catalonia, Chief Health Innovation Strategist	
Natalia Bursiewicz	Krakow Technology Park, Vice President of the Board	
Sergi Figuerola	i2Cat Foundation, Chief Technology and Innovation Officer, CTO @5GBarcelona	
Alba De Martino Rodríguez	Aragonese Institute of Health Sciences (IACS), Knowledge and Innovation Production Area, Director	
Xavier Càmara	Universitat Rovira i Virgili URV, Business Management Department director	

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José Martí	Valencian International University (VIU): (Vice-Rector for Research and Knowledge Transfer)	
Jaisiel Madrid	AMBIT – Living Spaces Cluster, Interiors Living Lab Manager	
Rosina Malagrida	IrsiCaixa AIDS Research Institute, Head of the Living Lab for Health	
Xavier Pérez	Fundación AEMA, Secretary	
Jürgen Howaldt	Chair of ESSI (European School of Social Innovation)	
Evdokimos Konstantinidis	European Network of Living Labs:, Leader of ASOSS Research Group at Medical Physics and Digital Innovation Lab, President of ENoLL, Project Coordinator VITALISE H2020, Project Coordinator RAISE HE.	
Toñi Caro	INTEGER's coordinator and National Appointed Representative in the Managing Committee. INTEGER / Net4AgeFriendly - International Interdisciplinary Network on Health and Wellbeing	

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- AFEdeMy
- F6S
- Krakow Technology Park
- Krakowia Jagiellonian University, Center for Evaluation and Analysis of Public Policies
- SHINE 2Europe
- Parc Sanitari Pere Virgili
- Memima baby
- Suara Cooperativa
- Living Lab Universidad de la Sabana
- EKA University of Applied Sciences
- Abdullah Gül University and Wellbeing Association

ANNEXES

Definitions of key concepts of the INTEGER thematic focus.

Healthy living by World Health Organisation (WHO)^{2,3}: A healthy lifestyle is a way of living that lowers the risk of being seriously ill or dying early. Not all diseases are preventable, but many deaths, particularly those from coronary heart disease and lung cancer, can be avoided. Scientific studies have identified certain types of behaviour that contribute to developing non-communicable diseases and early death. Health is not only just about avoiding disease. It is also about physical, mental and social well-being. When a healthy lifestyle is adopted, a more positive role model is provided to other family members, particularly children.

Figure: Age-friendly city domains according to the World Health Organisation https://www.researchgate.net/publication/313035642_Caregivers%27_Considerations_on_Age-friendly_Community_Features/figures?lo=1

Well-being by WHO: Traditionally, health was considered the absence of disease. In 1947 the WHO defined it as "a state of complete physical, mental and social well-being and not merely the absence of disease".

Physical well-being is when a person feels that none of his or her organs or functions is impaired; the body functions efficiently, and there is an appropriate physical capacity to respond to the various challenges of one's life activity.

² http://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/108180/EUR_ICP_LVNG_01_07_02.pdf, accessed December 7, 2022.

³ <https://www.betterup.com/blog/health-and-well-being>, accessed December 7, 2022.

Mental well-being is manifested through specific abilities: a) Learning and intellectual capacity, b) Processing information and acting on it, c) Discerning values and beliefs, d) Making well-thought-out decisions and putting them into practice and e) Understanding new ideas.

Social welfare could be said to be a notion that arose in response to the so-called "social question". The latter appeared in the 19th century, and is related to the sufferings of the working class due to the industrial revolution. It was echoed by intellectuals, politicians and religious people. In my opinion, it is complex to delimit, as it affects the relationships a person has with every aspect of his or her life. Such is the importance that I prefer to take a brief historical overview to understand it better.

ORGANIZATION	INITIATIVE	LINK
World Health Organization	World Health Organisation	https://www.who.int/
European Commission	The European Innovation Partnership on Active and Healthy Ageing (EIP on AHA)	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/eip-aha
European Commission	Directorate General Santé - Health and Food Safety	https://ec.europa.eu/info/departments/health-and-food-safety
	EIP on AHA: Repository of Innovative Practices & Reference Sites	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/active-and-healthy-living-digital-world/ecosystems-and-reference-sites/library/eip-aha-repository-innovative-practices-reference-sites
European Institute of Innovation & Technology	European Institute of Innovation & Technology	https://eit.europa.eu
Health	EIT Health - Promoting innovation in health	https://eithealth.eu/
Hands-on SHAFE	SHAFE-Smart Healthy Age-Friendly Environments ⁴	https://hands-on-shafe.eu/en/what-is-shafe
NET4 Age-Friendly	COST Action 19136 - Net4AgeFriendly -International interdisciplinary network on health and wellbeing in an age-friendly digital world	https://www.net4age.eu
VITALISE	Virtual Health and Wellbeing Living Lab Infrastructure	https://vitalise-project.eu/

⁴ Hands-on SHAFE was co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union, Key Action 204 Adult Education programme.

	<p>Social Innovation Responsive Environments Network</p>	<p>https://sireneproject.eu/</p>
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